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**A General Theorem for The Characterization
of N Prime Numbers Simultaneously**

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§1. ABSTRACT. This article presents a necessary and sufficient theorem as N numbers, coprime two by two, to be prime simultaneously.

It generalizes V. Popa's theorem [3], as well as I. Cucurezeanu's theorem ([1], p.165), Clement's theorem, S. Patrizio's theorems [2], etc.

Particularly, this General Theorem offers different characterizations for twin primes, for quadruple primes, etc.

§2. INTRODUCTION. It is evident the following:

Lemma 1. Let A, B be nonzero integers. Then:

$$AB \equiv 0(\text{mod } pB) \Leftrightarrow A \equiv 0(\text{mod } p) \Leftrightarrow A / p \text{ is an integer.}$$

Lemma 2. Let $(p, q) \sim 1, (a, p) \sim 1, (b, q) \sim 1$.

Then:

$$A \equiv 0(\text{mod } p)$$

and

$$B \equiv 0(\text{mod } q) \Leftrightarrow aAq + bBp \equiv 0(\text{mod } pq) \Leftrightarrow aA + bBp / q \equiv 0(\text{mod } p) \\ aA / p + bB / q \text{ is an integer.}$$

Proof:

The first equivalence:

We have $A = K_1p$ and $B = K_2q$ with $K_1, K_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$ hence

$$aAq + bBp = (aK_1 + bK_2)pq.$$

Reciprocal: $aAq + bBp = Kpq$, with $K \in \mathbb{Z}$ it results that $aAq \equiv 0(\text{mod } p)$ and $bBp \equiv 0(\text{mod } q)$, but from our assumption we find $A \equiv 0(\text{mod } p)$ and $B \equiv 0(\text{mod } q)$.

The second and third equivalence results from lemma1.

By induction we extend this lemma to the following:

Lemma 3. Let p_1, \dots, p_n be coprime integers two by two, and let a_1, \dots, a_n be integer numbers such that $(a_i, p_i) \sim 1$ for all i . Then

$$A_1 \equiv 0(\text{mod } p_1), \dots, A_n \equiv 0(\text{mod } p_n) \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n a_i A_i \prod_{j \neq i} p_j \equiv 0(\text{mod } p_1 \dots p_n) \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow (P / D) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i A_i / p_i) \equiv 0(\text{mod } P / D),$$

where $P = p_1 \dots p_n$ and D is a divisor of $p \Leftrightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n a_i A_i / p_i$ is an integer.

§3. From this last lemma we can find immediately a GENERAL THEOREM:

Let $P_{ij}, 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq m_i$, be coprime integers two by two, and let $r_1, \dots, r_n, a_1, \dots, a_n$ be integer numbers such that a_i be coprime with r_i for all i .

The following conditions are considered:

(i) $p_{i_1}, \dots, p_{i_{m_i}}$, are simultaneously prime if and only if $c_i \equiv 0 \pmod{r_i}$, for all i .

Then:

The numbers $p_{ij}, 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq m_i$, are simultaneously prime if and only if

$$(*) \quad (R/D) \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i c_i / r_i) \equiv 0 \pmod{R/D},$$

where $P = \prod_{i=1}^n r_i$ and D is a divisor of R .

Remark:

Often in the conditions (i) the module r_i is equal to $\prod_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{ij}$, or to a divisor of it, and in this case the relation of the General Theorem becomes:

$$(P/D) \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i c_i / \prod_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{ij}) \equiv 0 \pmod{P/D}$$

where

$$P = \prod_{i,j=1}^{n,m_i} p_{ij} \text{ and } D \text{ is a divisor of } P.$$

Corollaries:

We easily obtain that our last relation is equivalent with:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i c_i (P / \prod_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{ij})) \equiv 0 \pmod{P},$$

and

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i c_i / \prod_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{ij}) \text{ is an integer,}$$

etc.

The imposed restrictions for the numbers p_{ij} from the General Theorem are very wide, because if there would be two uncoprime distinct numbers, then at least one from these would not be prime, hence the $m_1 + \dots + m_n$ numbers might not be prime.

The General Theorem has many variants in accordance with the assigned values for the parameters a_1, \dots, a_n and r_1, \dots, r_m , the parameter D , as well as in accordance with the congruences c_1, \dots, c_n which characterize either a prime number or many other prime numbers simultaneously. We can start from the theorems (conditions c_i) which

characterize a single prime number (see Wilson, Leibnitz, F. Smarandache [4], or Simionov (p is prime if and only if $(p-k)!(k-1)!-(-1)^k \equiv 0(\text{mod } p)$, when $p \geq k \geq 1$; here, it is preferable to take $k = [(p+1)/2]$, where $[x]$ represents the greatest integer number $\leq x$, in order that the number $(p-k)!(k-1)!$ be the smallest possibly) for obtaining, by means of the General Theorem, conditions c'_j , which characterize many prime numbers simultaneously. Afterwards, from the conditions c_i, c'_j , using the General Theorem again, we find new conditions c''_h which characterize prime numbers simultaneously. And this method can be continued analogically.

Remarks

Let $m_i = 1$ and c_i represent the Simionov's theorem for all i

- (a) If $D=1$ it results in V. Popa's theorem, which generalizes in the Cucurezeanu's theorem and the last one generalizes in its turn Clement's theorem!
- (b) If $D = P / p_2$ and choosing conveniently the parameters a_i, k_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$, it results in S. Patrizio's theorem.

Several Examples:

1. Let p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n be positive integers >1 , coprime integers two by two, and $1 \leq k_i \leq p_i$ for all i . Then p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n are simultaneously prime if and only if:

$$(T) \sum_{i=1}^n [(p_i - k_i)!(k_i - 1)! - (-1)^{k_i}] \cdot \prod_{j \neq i} p_j \equiv 0(\text{mod } p_1 p_2 \dots p_n)$$

or

$$(U) \sum_{i=1}^n [(p_i - k_i)!(k_i - 1)! - (-1)^{k_i}] \cdot \prod_{j \neq i} p_j / (p_{s+1} \dots p_n) \equiv 0(\text{mod } p_1 \dots p_s)$$

or

$$(V) \sum_{i=1}^n [(p_i - k_i)!(k_i - 1)! - (-1)^{k_i}] \cdot p_j / p_i \equiv 0(\text{mod } p_j)$$

or

$$(W) \sum_{i=1}^n [(p_i - k_i)!(k_i - 1)! - (-1)^{k_i}] \cdot p_j / p_i \text{ is an integer.}$$

2. Another relation example (using the first theorem form [4]): p is a prime positive integer if and only if $(p-3)! - (p-1)/2 \equiv 0(\text{mod } p)$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n [(p_i - 3)! - (p_i - 1)/2] \cdot p_1 / p_i \equiv 0(\text{mod } p_1)$$

3. The odd numbers ... and ... are twin prime if and only if:
 $(p-1)!(3p+2)+2p+2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p(p+2)}$
 or
 $(p-1)!(p+2)-2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p(p+2)}$
 or
 $[(p-1)!+1]/p + [(p-1)!2+1]/(p+2)$ is an integer.
 These twin prime characterizations differ from Clement's theorem
 $((p-1)!4+p+4 \equiv 0 \pmod{p(p+2)})$

4. Let $(p, p+k) \sim 1$ then: p and $p+k$ are prime simultaneously if and only if

$$(p-1)!(p+k) + (p+k-1)!p + 2p+k \equiv 0 \pmod{p(p+k)},$$

which differs from I. Cucurezeanu's theorem ([1], p. 165):

$$k \cdot k![(p-1)!+1] + [K! - (-1)^k]p \equiv 0 \pmod{p(p+k)}$$

5. Look at a characterization of a quadruple of primes for
 $p, p+2, p+6, p+8$:

$[(p-1)!+1]/p + [(p-1)!2!+1]/(p+2) + [(p-1)!6!+1]/(p+6) + [(p-1)!8!+1]/(p+8)$
 be an integer.

6. For $p-2, p, p+4$ coprime integers tw by two, we find the relation:

$$(p-1)!+p[(p-3)!+1]/(p-2) + p[(p+3)!+1]/(p+4) \equiv -1 \pmod{p},$$

which differ from S. Patrizio's theorem

$$(8[(p+3)!/(p+4)] + 4[(p-3)!/(p-2)]) \equiv -11 \pmod{p}.$$

References

- [1] Cucurezeanu, I – Probleme de aritmetică și teoria numerelor, Ed. Tehnică, Bucharest, 1966.
 [2] Patrizio, Serafino – Generalizzazione del teorema di Wilson alle terne prime - Enseignement Math., Vol. 22(2), nr. 3-4, pp. 175-184, 1976.
 [3] Popa, Valeriu – Asupra unor generalizări ale teoremei lui Clement - Studii și Cercetări Matematice, Vol. 24, nr. 9, pp. 1435-1440, 1972.
 [4] Smarandache, Florentin – Criterii ca un număr natural să fie prim - Gazeta Matematică, nr. 2, pp. 49-52; 1981; see Mathematical Reviews (USA): 83a:10007.